

Crime Against Women In The Era Of Technology: Social Issues And Challenges

Paper Id : 19049 Submission Date : 14/05/2024 Acceptance Date : 21/05/2024 Publication Date : 25/05/2024
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.12657804

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Anuradha
Assistant Professor (Guest
Faculty)
Center For Distance And
Online Education
Punjabi University
Patiala, India

Abstract

Cybercrime against women has become an increasingly prevalent problem in recent years, with the rapid expansion of the digital world. Women are often targeted because they are perceived as vulnerable and easy targets. The current scenario and challenges of cybercrime against women are multifaceted and complex, and require a concerted effort from all stakeholders to address effectively. One of the most common forms of cybercrime against women is online harassment, which includes cyber stalking, cyber bullying, and revenge porn. Women are also frequently targeted through phishing scams, identity theft, and financial fraud. These crimes can have severe psychological, emotional, and financial consequences for the victims. One of the challenges in addressing cybercrime against women is that many victims are reluctant to report these crimes due to fear of retaliation, embarrassment, or stigma. This makes it difficult to accurately measure the scope of the problem and to develop effective strategies to prevent and respond to these crimes.[1] This requires a constant effort to update laws and regulations to address emerging threats, as well as to invest in training and resources for law enforcement and other stakeholders. There is a need for greater collaboration and coordination among various stakeholders, including law enforcement, technology companies, civil society organizations, and victims' groups. This includes sharing information, best practices, and resources to prevent and respond to cybercrime against women.[2]

This includes providing information on how to protect one online, as well as encouraging victim to report these crimes and seek support. Addressing cybercrime against women requires a multi-pronged approach that involves collaboration, coordination, and investment in resources and education. It is a complex and on-going challenge, but one that must be tackled to ensure the safety and well-being of women in the digital age.

Keywords Cybercrime, Women, Digitalisation, COVID-19, Cyber Stalking.

Introduction

Cybercrime against women is a growing problem that affects women worldwide. Women are often targeted for cybercrime due to their gender, with many forms of cybercrime being used to perpetuate violence, discrimination, and harassment against women.[3] This can include threatening messages, sexual harassment, and stalking online. Women are more likely than men to be victims of financial fraud, such as phishing scams and identity theft. This involves individuals using online platforms to build relationships with women with the aim of exploiting them sexually, financially, or emotionally. The COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated the problem of cybercrime against women, with many women being forced to work remotely and use online platforms more frequently. This has made them more vulnerable to cybercrime, including online harassment and cyber stalking.

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to examine the problems and challenges of increasing cyber crime against women in the present era of technology.

Review of Literature

For this paper many books, research papers, newspaper articles etc has been reviewed which has been discussed through out the paper.

Main Text

Despite the growing awareness of cybercrime against women, there are still many challenges in addressing this issue. These challenges include a lack of resources and training for law enforcement and other stakeholders, difficulty in accurately measuring the scope of the problem, underreporting due to fear of retaliation or stigma, and the rapidly evolving nature of technology and the internet. It is important to invest in education and awareness campaigns to promote gender equality and challenge sexist attitudes and behaviours. It is also important to improve the policies and practices of online platforms and social media companies to ensure that they are safe and inclusive spaces for women. The NCRB report also highlighted the importance of creating specialized cybercrime cells within law enforcement agencies and the need for capacity building and training of law enforcement personnel to investigate cybercrime cases effectively. The report also recommended that victims of cybercrime should be provided with support and counselling services to cope with the emotional and psychological impact of the crime. The NCRB report highlights the need for greater efforts to prevent and address cybercrime against women in India, including improving awareness and education, increasing resources and training for law enforcement, and providing support for victims.

Issues and Challenges

Issues and challenges in addressing cybercrime against women:

1. Underreporting of cybercrime due to fear of retaliation or stigma

Underreporting of cybercrime due to fear of retaliation or stigma is a significant challenge in addressing cybercrime against women. Some of the reasons for this challenge include: [4]

Fear of retaliation: Many victims of cybercrime may fear retaliation from their abuser or harasser if they report the crime. This fear can be justified as cybercriminals can easily use the internet to target victims even after they have reported the crime.

Stigma: There may be social stigma attached to cybercrime, particularly in cases involving non-consensual sharing of intimate or other forms of online harassment. Victims may be hesitant to report the crime due to concerns about how it will affect their reputation or relationships.

Lack of trust in the justice system: Some victims of cybercrime may not trust the justice system to take their complaint seriously or to adequately investigate and prosecute the crime.

Lack of awareness: Some victims of cybercrime may not be aware that what they have experienced constitutes a crime, particularly in cases where the crime involves non-consensual sharing of intimate images or other forms of online harassment.

Difficulty in accurately measuring the scope of the problem

Another significant challenge in addressing cybercrime against women is the difficulty in accurately measuring the scope of the problem. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:

Underreporting: Many victims of cybercrime do not report the crime to authorities due to fear of retaliation, shame, or a lack of trust in the justice system. This can make it difficult to accurately measure the scope of the problem.

Lack of standardized reporting: Even when cybercrime is reported, there may be inconsistencies in how it is defined and reported, making it difficult to accurately track and compare data across jurisdictions.

Incomplete data: Cybercrime data may be incomplete or missing critical information, such as the gender or demographic information of the victim,

Changing definitions: The definition of cybercrime is constantly evolving making it difficult to develop consistent and accurate measurements of the problem.

Lack of victim awareness: Some victims of cybercrime may not be aware that they have been victimized, particularly in cases where the crime involves non consensual sharing of intimate images or other forms of online harassment.

Rapidly evolving nature of technology and the internet

The rapidly evolving nature of technology and the internet presents a significant challenge in addressing cybercrime against women. Some of the specific challenges include:[5]

New forms of cybercrime: As technology evolves, new forms of cybercrime emerge, such as deep fakes, sextortion, and ransomware attacks. These crimes are often more sophisticated and difficult to detect than traditional forms of cybercrime.

Privacy concerns: New technologies, such as facial recognition and biometric data, raise privacy concerns and the potential for misuse by cybercriminals.

Lack of resources and training for law enforcement and other stakeholders

One of the challenges in addressing cybercrime against women is the lack of resources and training for law enforcement and other stakeholders. This includes:[6]

Limited resources: Many law enforcement agencies and other organizations tasked with addressing cybercrime may not have adequate resources, such as funding, technology, or personnel, to effectively investigate and respond to these crimes,

Limited training: Cybercrime is a complex and constantly evolving field, requiring specialized knowledge and skills. However, many law enforcement officers and other stakeholders may not have the necessary training and expertise to effectively investigate and respond to these crimes.

Lack of coordination: There may be a lack of coordination and collaboration between law enforcement agencies, technology companies, and other stakeholders involved in addressing cybercrime. This can lead to inefficiencies and gaps in the response to these crimes.

Limited data sharing: Law enforcement agencies and other organizations may not have access to the data and information necessary to investigate and respond to cybercrime effectively. This can make it difficult to identify and track cybercriminals and their activities.

Limited awareness and education among the general public, particularly women, about the risks and consequences of cybercrime

Limited awareness and education among the general public, particularly women, about the risks and consequences of cybercrime is a significant challenge in addressing cybercrime against women. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:

Lack of understanding: Many women may not fully understand the risks and consequences of cybercrime, including the potential harm to their privacy, reputation, and personal safety.

Limited resources: There may be limited resources available to provide education and awareness programs about cybercrime, particularly in developing countries or areas with limited access to technology.

Language barriers: In many regions, language barriers may prevent effective communication and dissemination of information about cybercrime.

Social norms: Social norms in some cultures may discourage women from speaking out about cybercrime or seeking support, which can limit awareness and education efforts.

Cybercriminals using advanced and sophisticated techniques to detection

Another significant challenge in addressing cybercrime where cybercriminals are using advanced and sophisticated techniques to evade. Some of the reasons for this challenge

include:[7]

Encryption: Cybercriminals may use encryption tools to hide their identity and communications, making it difficult for law enforcement to track and de them.

Anonymity: Cybercriminals may use anonymous networks, such as Tor, to mask their identity and evade detection.

Obfuscation: Cybercriminals may use obfuscation techniques to hide malicious code and other activities from security tools and software.

Collaboration: Cybercriminals may collaborate with other criminals or criminal groups to share resources, expertise, and technology to carry out sophisticated attacks.

Lack of international cooperation and coordination in addressing cybercrime

Cybercrime is another significant challenge in combatting cybercrime against women. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:[8]

Different legal frameworks: Countries have different legal frameworks for addressing cybercrime, which can create jurisdictional issues when investigating and prosecuting cybercrime.

Different law enforcement practices: Countries may have different law enforcement practices, resources, and capabilities, which can affect their ability to investigate and prosecute cybercrime effectively.

Limited information sharing: Countries may be hesitant to share information about cybercrime due to concerns about national security, privacy, and other legal or ethical considerations.

Lack of standardized data collection and reporting: There is a lack of standardized data collection and reporting on cybercrime, which makes it difficult to measure the scope and impact of cybercrime across different countries and regions,

Difficulty in tracking and prosecuting cybercriminals who operate across international borders

Some of the reasons for this challenge include:

Jurisdictional issues: Different countries have different legal frameworks and law enforcement practices, which can create jurisdictional issues when investigating and prosecuting cybercrime.

Lack of cooperation: Countries may be hesitant to cooperate with each other due to political, legal, or cultural differences, which can hinder cross-border investigations and prosecutions.

Use of anonymous networks: Cybercriminals may use anonymous networks, such as Tor, to mask their identity and evade detection, making it difficult for law enforcement agencies to track and identify them.

Lack of extradition treaties: Some countries may not have extradition treaties with other countries, which can make it difficult to extradite cybercriminals to face prosecution in another jurisdiction.

Limited availability of cybercrime forensic experts

The limited availability of cybercrime forensic experts is another significant challenge in addressing cybercrime against women. Cybercrime forensic experts are individuals with specialized knowledge and skills in the collection, analysis, and preservation of digital evidence related to cybercrime. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:[9]

High demand for expertise: The demand for cybercrime forensic experts is high due to the increasing prevalence and complexity of cybercrime. However, the supply of trained

experts is limited, making it difficult to meet the demand.

Rapidly evolving technology: Technology is rapidly evolving and cybercriminals are constantly developing new techniques and tools to evade detection. Cybercrime forensic experts need to stay up-to-date with the latest technology and trends to be effective, which can be challenging.

Lack of standardized training and certification: There is no standard or certification process for cybercrime forensic experts, which can be difficult to assess their skills and qualifications. This can also make it challenging to develop consistent and effective procedures for collecting and analysing digital evidence.

Lack of legal frameworks and regulations that address emerging forms of cybercrime

As technology evolves, new forms of cybercrime emerge, and existing laws and regulations may not be sufficient to address these new forms of cybercrime. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:

Slow pace of legislative action: The legislative process can be slow, and it may take time for laws and regulations to catch up with emerging forms of cybercrime.

Difficulty in defining and categorizing emerging forms of cybercrime: Emerging forms of cybercrime can be complex and difficult to define and categorize, making it challenging to develop effective laws and regulations.

Jurisdictional issues: Cybercrime can occur across borders, making it difficult to establish jurisdiction and enforce laws and regulations.

Limited access to legal remedies for victims of cybercrime

Cybercrime victims may face barriers to accessing justice, including lack of knowledge of their legal rights, limited resources to pursue legal action, and jurisdictional issues. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:[10]

Limited awareness of legal remedies: Many cybercrime victims may not be aware of their legal rights or the legal remedies available to them.

Financial barriers: Pursuing legal action can be expensive, and many cybercrime victims may not have the financial resources to hire lawyers or pursue legal action.

Jurisdictional issues: Cybercrime can occur across borders, making it difficult to establish jurisdiction and enforce legal remedies.

Insufficient funding for cybercrime prevention and response

Insufficient funding for cybercrime prevention and response is a significant challenge in combating cybercrime against women. Funding is essential to developing and implementing effective strategies to prevent and respond to cybercrime, including investing in cyber security technologies and tools, developing public awareness campaigns, providing training and support to law enforcement agencies, and supporting victim services. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:[11]

Limited resources: Many countries and organizations may not have the financial resources to invest in cybercrime prevention and response.

Lack of understanding of the impact of cybercrime: Some stakeholders may not fully understand the impact of cybercrime on individuals and society, and therefore may not prioritize funding for prevention and response efforts.

Competing priorities: Governments and organizations may have competing priorities for their funding, which can make it challenging to allocate resources to cybercrime prevention and response.

Difficulty in removing offensive content from the internet

Offensive content such as revenge porn, hate speech, and online harassment can have a long-lasting impact on victims and can contribute to a toxic online environment. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:

The vastness of the internet: There are billions of websites and online platforms, making it difficult to monitor and remove offensive content from all of them.

Lack of clear legal frameworks: There may be a lack of clear legal frameworks that govern the removal of offensive content from the internet.

Inadequate enforcement mechanisms: Even if legal frameworks are in place there may be inadequate enforcement mechanisms to ensure that off content is removed.

Lack of cooperation from social media platforms and other technology companies in addressing cybercrime

Social media platforms and other technology companies have a significant impact on the online environment, and their policies and practices can have a profound effect on the prevalence of cybercrime. Some of the reasons for this challenge include;

Limited legal requirements: In some jurisdictions, there may be limited legal requirements for social media platforms and other technology companies to address cybercrime.

Differences in policies: Social media platforms and other technology companies may have different policies regarding the reporting and removal of offensive content, which can make it challenging to address cybercrime in a consistent manner.

Lack of resources: Social media platforms and other technology companies may not have the resources to invest in effective strategies for preventing and responding to cybercrime.

Inadequate protection for victims of cybercrime, including victims of revenge porn and online harassment

Inadequate protection for victims of cybercrime, including victims of revenge porn and online harassment, is a significant challenge in combating cybercrime against women. Victims of cybercrime may experience significant harm, including emotional distress, reputational damage, and financial losses. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:[12]

Limited legal frameworks: In some jurisdictions, there may be limited legal frameworks that provide protection for victims of cybercrime.

Inadequate enforcement mechanism. Even if legal frameworks are in place, there may be inadequate enforcement mechanisms to ensure that victims receive protection and support.

Stigma and shame: Victims of cybercrime may experience stigma and shame, which can make it difficult for them to come forward and seek support.

The possibility of false accusations and misuse of cybercrime laws against innocent individuals

The possibility of false accusations and misuse of cybercrime laws against innocent individuals is a challenge in combating cybercrime against women. False accusations and misuse of laws can have significant consequences for individuals, including reputational damage, legal costs, and even criminal penalties. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:[13]

Lack of understanding of cybercrime laws: Many people may not fully understand the scope and limitations of cybercrime laws, which can lead to misunderstandings and misuse of these laws.

Malicious intent: Some individuals may use cybercrime laws to make false accusations against others for malicious purposes, such as revenge or harassment.

Inadequate safeguards: In some cases, there may be inadequate safeguards in place to prevent false accusations or misuse of cybercrime laws.

Limited capacity of law enforcement agencies to investigate and respond to cybercrime

Cybercrime is a significant challenge in combating cybercrime against women. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:[14]

The complexity of cybercrime: Cybercrime is a complex and ever-evolving area of criminal activity that requires specialized skills and resources to investigate effectively.

Insufficient funding: Many law enforcement agencies may not have sufficient funding to invest in the technology and training necessary to efficiently investigate and respond to cybercrime.

Lack of expertise: Law enforcement agencies may not have sufficient expertise in cybercrime investigation, which can make it difficult for them to identify and apprehend perpetrators.

Difficulty in distinguishing between criminal and non-criminal behavior online

Online is a challenge in combating cybercrime against women. Some of the reason this challenge include:

Lack of clear legal definitions: Many countries may not have clear legal definitions of what constitutes cybercrime, which can make it difficult to distinguish between criminal and non-criminal behaviours online.

Difficulty in identifying intent: In some cases, it may be difficult to determine whether an individual's actions online are criminal or not, particularly if the intent behind those actions is unclear.

Cultural differences: What may be considered acceptable behaviour in one culture or society may be considered criminal in another, which can create challenges in distinguishing between criminal and non-criminal behaviour online.

Limited access to support services and counselling for victims of cybercrime

Cybercrime is a challenge in combating cybercrime against women. Some of the reasons for this challenge include:

Lack of awareness: Many victims of cybercrime may not be aware of the support services and counselling options available to them, or may not know how to access those services.

Limited availability of services: In some areas, there may be limited availability of support services and counselling options for victims of cybercrime. particularly in rural or remote areas.

The potential for cybercrime to contribute to gender-based violence and discrimination

The potential for cybercrime to contribute to gender-based violence and discrimination significant challenge in combating cybercrime against women. Some of the ways in which cybercrime can contribute to gender-based violence and discrimination include:[15]

Conclusion

Online harassment: Women are more likely than men to experience online harassment, which can include threats, stalking, and bullying. This harassment can have a significant impact on the mental and emotional well-being of victims, and can contribute to a culture of gender-based violence and discrimination.

Revenge porn: Revenge porn, which involves the non-consensual sharing of intimate images, is a form of gender-based violence that can have long-lasting consequences for victims. It can lead to victim blaming and shaming, and can contribute to a culture in which women are objectified and dehumanized.

Discrimination in online spaces: Women may experience discrimination and harassment in online spaces, including social media platforms and online forums. This discrimination can include sexist comments, harassment, and exclusion from online conversations and communities.

Challenges Police

Cybercrime against women in India is a growing concern, and there are several challenges that the police face in investigating and addressing these crimes. Some of the challenges include:

Lack of awareness: Many women are not aware of the laws and resources available to them to report and address cybercrimes. This makes it difficult for the police to investigate and prosecute these crimes.

Limited resources: Many police departments lack the resources and technology necessary to investigate and address cybercrimes. This can hinder their ability to identify and track down perpetrators.

Social stigma: Victims of cybercrime may face social stigma and shame, which can prevent them from reporting the crime to the police. This can make it difficult for the police to identify and address these crimes.

Jurisdictional issues: Cybercrime can often cross state and national borders, making it difficult for the police to investigate and prosecute these crimes.

Technical challenges: Cybercrime can involve complex technical issues, such as encryption and anonymity, which can make it difficult for the police to identify and track down perpetrators.

Cyber Cells

In India, cybercrime against women is a growing concern, and cyber cells have been established in several cities to address these crimes. However, these cyber cells also face several challenges in investigating and addressing cybercrime against women. Some of the challenges include:

Limited resources: Cyber cells in India often lack the resources and technology necessary to investigate and address cybercrime. This can make it difficult for them to identify and track down perpetrators.

Lack of awareness: Many women are not aware of the cyber cells or the resources available to them to report and address cybercrime. This makes it difficult for the cyber cells to investigate and prosecute these crimes.

Jurisdictional issues: Cybercrime can often cross state and national borders, making it difficult for the cyber cells to investigate and prosecute these crimes.

Technical challenges: Cybercrime can involve complex technical issues, such as encryption and anonymity, which can make it difficult for the cyber cells to identify and track down perpetrators.

Social stigma: Victims of cybercrime may face social stigma and shame, which can prevent them from reporting the crime to the cyber cells. This can make it difficult for the cyber cells to identify and address these crimes.

Judiciary

The judiciary in India plays a crucial role in addressing cybercrime against women, but they also face several challenges in effectively prosecuting and punishing perpetrators. Some of the challenges include:

Lack of awareness and training: Judges and lawyers may lack the awareness and training necessary to understand the complexities of cybercrime and its impact on women. This can make it difficult for them to prosecute and punish perpetrators effectively.

Technical challenges: Cybercrime can involve complex technical issues, such as encryption and anonymity, which can make it difficult for judges and lawyers to understand the evidence and make informed decisions.

Slow legal process: The legal process in India can be slow, which can cause delays in prosecuting and punishing perpetrators of cybercrime against women. This can be particularly harmful for victims who are seeking justice and closure.

Social stigma and victim blaming: Victims of cybercrime against women may face social stigma and victim blaming, which can impact their ability to seek justice through the legal system. This can make it difficult for judges and lawyers to prosecute and punish perpetrators effectively.

Limited resources: The judiciary in India may lack the resources and technology necessary to effectively prosecute and punish perpetrators of cybercrime against women. This can hinder their ability to address these crimes effectively.

Government

The government in India has a critical role to play in addressing cybercrime against women, but they also face several challenges in effectively addressing this issue. Some of the challenges include:

Lack of comprehensive legislation: While there are some laws in place to address cybercrime against women in India, there is a need for comprehensive legislation that addresses all forms of cybercrime and provides adequate punishment to perpetrators.

Limited resources: The government may lack the resources and technology necessary to effectively investigate and address cybercrime against women. This can hinder their ability to identify and track down perpetrators.

Social stigma and victim blaming: Victims of cybercrime against women may face social stigma and victim blaming, which can make it difficult for them to report the crime to the authorities. This can hinder the government's ability to address these crimes effectively.

Jurisdictional issues: Cybercrime can often cross state and national borders, making it difficult for the government to investigate and prosecute these crimes.

Lack of awareness and education: Many women are not aware of the laws and resources available to them to report and address cybercrime. This makes it difficult for the government to investigate and prosecute these crimes.

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